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Entrepreneurial Skills and Operational Efficiency of Small-Scale Businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District

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Abstract

The study examined the influence of entrepreneurial skills on the operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District, Nigeria. Two research questions and two hypotheses, derived from the study's specific objectives, guided the investigation. A descriptive survey design was adopted. The population comprised 890 managers of small-scale businesses in the district, from which a sample of 274 was drawn using the Taro Yamane formula. A simple random sampling technique was employed in selecting the participants, and data were collected using a researcher-developed instrument titled Entrepreneurial Skills and Operational Efficiency of Small-Scale Businesses Questionnaire (ESOESSBQ). The instrument was face-validated by three research experts. Its reliability was established using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding a coefficient of 0.85, indicating an acceptable level of internal consistency. Data were analysed using simple linear regression, and the hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The analysis revealed, among others, that marketing skills and innovative skills had a very low level of influence on the operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in the study area. Based on the findings, it was recommended, among others, that the state government should organise seminars and workshops to train and equip managers of small-scale enterprises with marketing skills to enhance the effective operation of their businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial skills, marketing skills, innovative skills, small scale businesses, operation.

Introduction

The sustainable economic development of any nation depends largely on the operational efficiency of small-scale businesses. It is one of the major catalysts for any economic development, as it contributes significantly to stimulating economic growth through the creation of employment opportunities, poverty reduction, development of local raw materials, creation of a more competitive and healthier market, contribution to Gross Domestic Products (GDP) and improvement in the standard of living, among others. Small-scale businesses have been identified as having enormous potential for long-term development. Brandy (2020) opined that small-scale businesses are those enterprises where business is done on a small scale. Small businesses have few employees, limited capital investment and a small scale of operation. Harrison (2018) asserted that operation of small-scale businesses requires creativity, risk-taking, and innovation, as well as the ability to plan and manage projects in order to achieve objectives. Key operating activities for most small-scale businesses include manufacturing, selling, advertising, marketing activities, and provision of services, among others, which require entrepreneurial skills.

Entrepreneurial skills refer to the set of competencies and abilities that enable individuals to identify, evaluate, and pursue entrepreneurial opportunities (Barba-Sánchez and Atienza-Sahuquillo, 2018). These skills include, but are not limited to, problem-solving, decision-making, risk-taking, innovation, and opportunity recognition. Entrepreneurial skills help to create wealth, self-direction, and satisfying careers while also adding value to society's well-being. It helps entrepreneurs to make informed business decisions and choose who to do the business with. For efficient operation of small-scale businesses, entrepreneurial skills such as marketing, creativity, decision-making, organising, recognising and utilising opportunities, communication, networking, team-building, goal-setting and problem-solving skills are needed to survive.

Acquisition of effective entrepreneurial skills in small-scale businesses promotes profitability and ensures their operational sustainability. Entrepreneurial skills, according to Frank (2021), help small-scale businesses to maintain optimal and effective operations. It is therefore crucial for owners of small-scale businesses to adopt suitable entrepreneurial skills in their daily business operations. As observed by Utop (2019), entrepreneurial skills include communication skills, time management skills, innovative skills, customer retention skills, marketing skills, teamwork, problem-solving, leadership skills, planning and organising, self-management, learning skills and technology skills, among others. Jones (2018) noted that in this competitive business environment, whether entrepreneurs are starting a new venture or driving growth in an existing business, having a strong entrepreneurial skill set is a key determinant of long-term success and financial stability. Although there exist several

entrepreneurial skills that can promote effective operation of small-scale businesses, this study focuses on marketing skills and innovative skills.

Marketing skills refer to the abilities and competencies that enable small-scale business owners to effectively identify, reach and satisfy their target customers (Kotler and Keller, 2020). These skills encompass a range of activities, including market research, product development, pricing strategies, promotional techniques and customer relationship management. For small-scale businesses, marketing skills are crucial for their operational efficiency and overall competitiveness (Reijonen, 2020). Marketing skills are certain invaluable skill sets that have incredible potential to persuade, sell and build lasting customer relationships. Effective marketing strategies can help small-scale businesses to better understand their target market, differentiate their products or services, and create customer loyalty, all of which contribute to their operational efficiency (Cacciolatti and Lee, 2021).

Small-scale business owners who possess strong marketing skills are better equipped to make informed decisions, allocate resources efficiently, and respond to changes in the market. According to Gonad (2020), marketing skills are skills that allow marketers to build a brand, explain that brand, identify a target market and sell products within the market. It is the strategy that drives a business to growth and operational sustainability. Instead of focusing on short-term results, marketing skills help win customers for the long haul by ensuring long-term brand affinity and loyalty (Landi, 2019). With the right tactics, marketing skills boost product sales and increase profit (Kaulu, 2018). Effective marketing skills help to build a company's reputation (Poup, 2017). Effective marketing skills help to bring consumers and products together. Poup (2017) noted that the importance of marketing skills in a business is that it makes the customers aware of products or services, engages them and helps them make the buying decision.

James (2019) noted that marketing for business is a highly valuable tool, as it helps to create brand awareness, drive profit and growth, acquire and retain customers, and enhance engagement. Fadima (2020) reported that effective marketing strategies play a pivotal role in establishing a strong presence in the market and connecting with the target audience. Codi (2019) opined that marketing skills are fundamental in promoting products and services through a series of strategic steps. They begin by conducting thorough market research to understand consumer preferences, market trends, and competitor strategies. By identifying target audiences based on demographics, consumer psychology and behaviour patterns, marketers can tailor their campaigns effectively. The ultimate goal of marketing skills is to enhance brand visibility, boost sales and cultivate lasting relationships with customers through innovative marketing tactics that resonate with their target audience.

Marketing skills help the organisation to understand the desires and aversions of potential customers. Marketing, especially in this digital age, is continuously shifting

and requires a marketer who can adapt and devise effective strategies to compete favourably and deliver results. One of the keys to being adaptable and agile in marketing is having a deep understanding of the business target audience. By knowing their needs, preferences, and behaviours, marketers can tailor their marketing approach to better resonate with them. This requires ongoing research, data analysis, and testing to ensure that the marketing efforts are meeting the needs of the target audience. Marketing skills help to enhance effective business operations. Alieu (2017) showed that marketing skills have significant influence on the operation of small-sized businesses. Also, Imou (2018) revealed that marketing skills have significant influence on the operation of small-sized businesses. In an environment where there are drastic changes as a result of technological revolution, innovative skills have become one of the most important factors necessary for the efficient operation and sustainable growth of small-scale businesses.

Innovative skills are one of the most important entrepreneurial skills that are needed in any business enterprise to facilitate and enhance effective operation. Udukeke and Usoro (2023) defined innovation as the application of a better solution that meets new requirements, unarticulated needs or existing market needs. It is the implementation of a new or significantly improved product (goods or services). Innovation is the process of creating something new or introducing new ways, methods or techniques of doing things. Yeh-Yunlin and Chen (2017) described innovation as an idea, practice or object that appears recent to people or the adoption unit. Innovation is the application of a better solution that meets new requirements, unarticulated needs, or existing market needs. Abraham (2015) defines innovation as the implementation of a new or significantly improved product (goods and services). This is accomplished through more effective products, processes, services, technologies, or business models that are not readily available to markets, governments and society. Wan *et al.* (2015) defined innovation as a process that involves the generation, adoption and implementation of new ideas or practices within the organisation. Tidd *et al.* (2016) referred to innovation as a process of turning opportunity into new ideas and of putting these ideas into widely used practice.

The possession and effective utilisation of innovative skills can be a key differentiator for small-scale businesses, enabling them to adapt to changing market conditions, develop unique products or services, and enhance their overall operational efficiency and performance. In the context of small-scale businesses, innovative skills encompass a wide range of capabilities, including creative thinking, problem-solving, adaptability, risk-taking, collaboration and networking. Heenkenda *et al.* (2022) confirmed that innovation is the backbone of successful businesses in the world, as it is concerned with the capacity to continuously turn information and ideas into new products, systems and processes that will benefit the firm and the stakeholders involved.

Organisational innovation has been a dominant factor in maintaining worldwide competitiveness. It fuels organisational growth and drives future success. Small-scale businesses must constantly seek new knowledge, ideas and skills for introducing new goods and services or improving and renewing existing ones if they wish to keep or capture market shares and remain competitive. According to Henderson and Clark in Hager in Udukeke and Usoro (2023), innovation can be classified into incremental innovation (routine innovation), architectural innovation, radical innovation, disruptive innovation and disruptive innovation.

Incremental involves relatively small modifications to preexisting technological competencies. It improves and extends established designs and features to increase value to customers. Improvement takes place in individual components, but the basic core design concepts and the linkage between them remain the same. The essence of architectural innovation is to reconfigure an already established system to link together components and parts in a new way. The change is so small that the core concept behind the changed component is the same, and the associated scientific and engineering knowledge remains the same. Radical innovation gives birth to new enterprises or products (or absorbs existing ones) and involves creating revolutionary technology or breakthroughs. Disruptive innovation requires a new business model but not necessarily a technological breakthrough. For that reason, it also challenges or disrupts the business models of other companies. All these innovations could occur in products, processes, services, among others.

Innovation is also a long-term performance indicator which is integrated with concepts like change, creativity, improvement and risk-taking for the firms; competition mostly shapes around the customer. Luecke and Katz in Udukeke and Usoro (2023) explained that creativity is often the basis for innovation. For innovation to occur, there must be a creative idea as well as the ability to convert that idea into action to make a difference. According to the authors, innovation is, therefore, the successful implementation of creative ideas. Hence, the result of necessity and creativity is innovation. In addition, innovation is based on multiple and simultaneous influences of individual and collective determinants. Laforet and Tann (2016) posited that these determinants are introduced to be culture and leadership, which are two of the relevant internal conditions of innovation. Smith (2018) posits that culture relates to the values and beliefs of the organisation and how the ability to manage affects innovation, the motivation from a leadership supporting innovation, the willingness to exchange knowledge and the targeted promotion of innovators within the firm.

The ability to lead, direct, and support the creation and sustaining of innovation behaviours is important for a firm. The importance of leadership style as seen by Harborne and Johnne (2017) lies in the opportunities of the leader to directly decide on how to introduce new ideas into an organisation, set specific goals, and encourage innovation initiatives to employees. This is because leadership that fosters innovation

enables setting task boundaries, sharing information, obtaining resources, instilling a positive attitude and a leadership style that keeps the employees challenged and focused (McDonough, 2015). Furthermore, an appropriate work climate is crucial for innovation. Work climate is one of the enablers that create opportunity for innovation.

Firms need to create a favourable working condition that is tolerant of the mistakes that will occur and allow for recovery and learning from failures. Van *et al.* (2017) showed that openness towards knowledge sharing is important in reinforcing innovation. Since small-scale businesses operate in a highly dynamic and rapidly changing environment, creation of an appropriate work climate is not a secondary choice for contemporary business organisations; rather, it is vital to ensure substantial merit-based excellence under the intense global competition. Olughor (2015) suggested that important issues for an employee to be innovative are the belief that innovation is important, willingness to take risks and willingness to exchange ideas. Abiodun and Ibidun (2017) emphasised that the firm's innovation performance depends on the opportunities provided by their external environment.

This implies that SMEs become very competitive in an emerging market when attention is given to innovative products and processes that build their reputation in the market environment. Essentially, innovation creates the desire for firms to obtain increased business performance and a competitive edge. Udukeke and Usoro added that innovation provides the following benefits: allows businesses to expand their customer base by refreshing the market with new and improved products; acts as a key component of competitive advantage and helps companies stay ahead of competitors; supports the ability to charge at a premium; provides incremental revenue; and also increases shareholders' values and creates a good reputation for an organisation. Heenkenda *et al.* (2022) confirmed that innovation is the backbone of successful businesses around the world, as it is concerned with the capacity to continuously turn information and ideas into new products, systems and processes that will benefit the firm and the stakeholders involved.

Extensive proof from past research has shown that innovation influenced firm efficiency. Product improvement approach is one of the key elements that help firms to take a competitive edge. Ojenike (2024) stressed that the performance of SMEs is connected with SMEs capability to invent an innovative product that can meet customers' specifications and wants. Osei *et al.* (2016) asserted that innovation is the key mechanism of development strategies for entering fresh markets, entering the current profit-enhancing market and giving SMEs a competitive advantage.

In the same vein, Foroudi *et al.* (2016) reported that innovation significantly adds value to firm performance. Eze *et al.* (2016) confirmed that firms are continually seeking to get rid of their traditional method of developing fresh processes to decrease costs, enhance production quality, decrease lead times or boost client value. Furthermore, a recent study by Kaleka and Morgan (2019) observed that product

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innovation capability has a direct relationship with firms' efficiency. Extensive proof from past studies has shown that innovation skills have a substantial effect on the operational efficiency of small-scale businesses, and that has helped most of the firms that have adopted them in gaining a competitive advantage over their rivals.

Ojenike (2024) found that product innovation strategy has significant influence on product quality of selected representatives of SMEs, and process innovation strategy has significant influence on sales volume quality of selected representatives of SMEs. Ukabuduzhiimkpa and Onuoha (2023) showed that there is a significant and positive relationship between the dimensions of innovative capability and the measures of survival. Hence, for firms to survive in the ever-changing environment, there is a need to tap into technological and product innovation. Based on this background, the present study determined the influence of entrepreneurial skills on operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Statement of the problem

Despite providing a share of global employment, small-scale businesses still face major challenges when it comes to working conditions and productivity. As the national economy shrinks and social and economic policies impact the economy, large enterprises can invest more in training and equipment, pay higher wages and offer better working conditions, and so outmatch small-scale businesses when it comes to productivity and operational efficiency. Small-scale businesses that will survive will have to turn to core entrepreneurial skills to drive innovation and creativity. A cursory analysis reveals that small-scale businesses are struggling and that proprietors and directors of small-scale businesses are short of entrepreneurial skills essential for survival and growth. These problems could be attributed to poor management of finances, lack of trained and qualified personnel, poor accounting skills, lack of patronage, lack of proper accountability and lack of entrepreneurial skills such as marketing skills, customers' retention skills, innovative skills, communication skills and time management skills, among others. These prevalent challenges may have resulted in declining profits and subsequent winding up of most small-scale businesses.

This has a negative effect on the creation of employment, leading to an increase in the rate of unemployment and poverty with a direct effect on internally generated revenue accruable to the state. While several studies have explored the broader challenges and success factors for small-scale businesses in Nigeria, the specific influence of entrepreneurial skills on the operational efficiency of these enterprises in the Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District context has not been extensively investigated. It is against this backdrop that the present study aims to investigate the influence of entrepreneurial skills, with a specific focus on marketing skills, customers' retention skills, innovative skills, communication skills and time management skills on the operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial

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District, Nigeria. By addressing this research problem, the study can provide valuable insights that can inform the development of policies, training programmes, and support mechanisms to help small-scale business owners in the region cultivate and effectively leverage their innovative skills, leading to improved operational efficiency, competitiveness, and long-term sustainability.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study was to determine the influence of entrepreneurial skills on operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. Determine the extent to which marketing skills influence operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.
- ii. Determine the extent to which innovative skills influence operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- i. What is the extent to which marketing skills influence operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District?
- ii. What is the extent to which innovative skills influence operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- H₀₁:** There is no significant Influence of marketing skills on the operational efficiency of small-scale Businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant Influence of innovative skills on the operational efficiency of small-scale Businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.

Research Methods

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The study was carried out in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District. The population of the study comprised 890 small-scale business managers in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District. A total of 274 managers constituted the sample for the study. The sample was determined statistically using the Taro Yamane formula. A simple random sampling technique was adopted in selecting the sample size from the population. The instrument entitled “Entrepreneurial Skills and Operational Efficiency of Small-Scale Businesses Questionnaire (ESOESSBQ)” was used in collecting data for this study. The instrument was divided into three sections: A, B, C and D. Section A sought information from respondents on

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demographic variables, while sections B and C contained items on the independent variables' entrepreneurial skills (marketing skills and innovative skills), and section D contained information on the dependent variable (operational efficiency of small-scale businesses). Respondents were expected to indicate by ticking (√) the information provided as they relate with the items. The response options were Very High Extent (VHE) = 5 points, High Extent (HE) = 4 points, Moderate Extent (ME) = 3 points, Low Extent (LE) = 2 points, Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1 point. The instrument was face-validated by three research experts. The internal consistency of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha statistical analysis, and the overall reliability coefficient of .85 was obtained. The researcher administered the instruments to the respondents in each of the small-scale businesses selected for the study. Simple linear regression was used to answer all the research questions and test the null hypotheses at .05 level of significance.

Data Presentation and Results

Research Question 1

What is the extent to which marketing skills influence operational efficiency of small-scale Businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District?

Table 1: Simple Regression Analysis of the Extent to Which Marketing Skills Influence Operational Efficiency of Small-Scale Businesses

Variables	R	R²	% Influence
Marketing Skills	.631	.398	39.8
Operational Efficiency			

The result in Table 1 shows the value of the regression coefficient (R) and its corresponding R² of .631 and .398 respectively. The value of R² of .398 indicates that marketing skills have a 39.8% influence on the variation in operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District. This implies that to a very low extent marketing skills influence operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in the study area.

Research Question 2

What is the extent to which innovation skills influence of operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District?

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Table 2: Simple Regression Analysis of the Extent to Which Innovation Skills Influence Operational Efficiency of Small-Scale Businesses

Variables	R	R ²	% Influence
Innovation Skills	.607	.368	36.8
Operational Efficiency			

The result in Table 2 shows the value of the regression coefficient (R) and its corresponding R² of .607 and .368 respectively. The value of R² of .368 indicates that innovation skills have a 36.8% influence on the variation in operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District. This implies that to a very low extent innovation skills influence operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant influence of marketing skills on the operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.

Table 4.5: Regression Analysis of the Influence of Marketing Skills on the Operational Efficiency of Small-Scale Business

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1390.108	1	1390.108	177.256	.000 ^b
Residual	2101.759	268	7.842		
Total	3491.867	269			

a. Dependent Variable: Operational Efficiency Skills

b. Predictors: (Constant), Marketing Skill

The result in Table 3 shows that the R-value of .631 and the F-value of 177.256 are significant. This is because the p-value of .000 is less than .05 level of significance at 1 and 268 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant influence of influence of marketing skills on the operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District is rejected. This means that marketing skills have significant influence on operational efficiency of small-scale businesses.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant influence of innovation skills on the operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.

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Table 4: Regression Analysis of the Influence of Innovation Skills on the Operational Efficiency of Small-Scale Business

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1285.806	1	1285.806	156.204	.000 ^b
Residual	2206.061	268	8.232		
Total	3491.867	269			

a. Dependent Variable: Operational Efficiency Skills

b. Predictors: (Constant), Innovation Skills

The result in Table 4 shows that the R-value of .607 and the F-value of 156.204 are significant. This is because the p-value of .000 is less than .05 level of significance at 1 and 268 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant influence of innovation skills on the operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District is rejected. Hence, there is significant influence of innovation skills on the operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in the study area.

Summary of Findings

The following findings were obtained from the study:

1. Marketing skills have a very low extent of influence on operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.
2. Innovative skills have a very low extent of influence on operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.
3. Marketing skills significantly influence operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.
4. Innovation skills significantly influence operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the analysis on marketing skills and operational efficiency of small-scale businesses showed that there is a very low extent of influence of marketing skills on operational efficiency of small-scale businesses. This implied that operational efficiency of small-scale businesses is as a result of marketing. The corresponding hypothesis shows that there is a significant influence of marketing skills on the operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District. This finding may be attributed to the fact that marketing skills are effective in enhancing the operations of small-scale businesses.

This finding is in line with the earlier result of James (2019) that marketing for business is a highly valuable tool that requires skills, as it helps to create brand awareness, drive profit and growth, acquire and retain customers, and enhance

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engagement. Fadima (2020) reported that effective marketing strategies play a pivotal role in establishing a strong presence in the market and connecting with the target audience. Codi (2019) found that marketing skills are fundamental in promoting products and services through a series of strategic steps. This begins by conducting thorough market research to understand consumer preferences, market trends, and competitor strategies. By identifying target audiences based on demographics, consumer psychology and behaviour patterns, marketers can tailor their campaigns effectively.

The result of the analysis on innovative skills and operational efficiency of small-scale businesses showed that there is a very low extent of influence of customers' retention skills on operational efficiency of small-scale businesses. The result of the corresponding hypothesis indicated that there is significant influence of customers' retention skills on the operations of small businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District. This result may be due to the fact that innovation skills have the potential to enhance the operations of small businesses.

The finding is supported by Ojenike (2024), who found that product innovation strategy has significant influence on product quality of selected representatives of SMEs and process innovation strategy has significant influence on sales volume quality of selected representatives of SMEs. Similarly, Ukabuduzhiimkpa and Onuoha (2023) confirmed that there is a significant and positive relationship between the dimensions of innovative capability and the measures of survival.

Therefore, for firms to survive the ever-changing environment, there is a need to tap into technological and product innovation. The study is in agreement with the findings of Nwankwo and Ezeibe (2021), who found that product innovation, process innovation, market innovation and administrative innovation have significant influence on the financial performance of small and medium-scale enterprises. Thus, when innovative skills become a priority in a business firm, it helps in *the effective operation of the business*.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that entrepreneurial skills can influence the operational efficiency of small-scale businesses in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District, Nigeria, as marketing and innovative skills were revealed to influence operational efficiency of small-scale businesses.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. State Government should organise seminars and workshop to train and equip small-scale business enterprises managers with marketing skills for effective operation of these business enterprises in the study area.

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- ii. Small business owners should employ diverse innovative skills in order to compete favourably in the ever-changing market, retain their customers and ensure operational sustainability.

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